

Using Signal-detection Theory & IRT Methods with Multiple Response Items

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Background

- TEI becoming more widespread
 - Item response types are expanding
- One useful type of item: Multiple response (MR)
 - Similar to MC, but allows for multiple correct options
 - Select some subset of the response options
 - Instructions can induce different cognitive sets
 - ‘Select all ...’ vs. ‘Select N ...’ vs. ‘Select the top N ...’
- Allows for a wide range of constructs to be measured
 - Cue recognition, take action, identify risk clusters, evaluate outcomes
- Generally scored as right/wrong
 - Must select only the correct keys
 - Tend to be more difficult → might be similar to most difficult threshold in a GRM

Examples

Read the following case study, then refer to the case study to answer the questions.

Time: 1300

The nurse is caring for a client who had surgery for a left femur fracture 24 hours ago. The client has an allergy to latex and has a ventriculoperitoneal shunt on the left side that was placed in infancy. A left long leg fiberglass cast was applied following surgery. The client received morphine intravenously one hour ago for incisional pain. Vital signs are: temperature 99.2° F (37.3° C), pulse 126, respirations 16, blood pressure 124/82, oxygen saturation 93%. The client is awake but irritable, and is shouting "Take this cast off!"

To perform a neurovascular assessment for the client, which of the following actions should the nurse take? Select all that apply.

- Palpate to determine the temperature of the left foot.
- Press down gently on the client's shoulders and ask the client to try to lift the shoulders.
- Palpate to determine the temperature of the left upper thigh.
- Check the client's pupils for reactivity to light.
- Check and compare the client's pedal pulses.
- Determine whether the client can wiggle the left toes.
- Note the color of the left foot.
- Ask the client, "Can you feel a squeeze of the toes on the left foot?"
- Determine how quickly color returns to the nailbed after the nurse squeezes the left great toe.
- Ask the client, "Can you tell me the current day and time?"
- Ask the client, "Can you tell me your name?"
- Ask the client, "Can you tell me where you are right now?"

Read the following case study, and then refer to the case study to answer the question.

The client is a 32-year-old, African American female who works as a high school teacher and was admitted to the hospital after reporting epigastric pain for 2 days. The client was diagnosed with cholecystitis and subsequently had an open cholecystectomy 24 hours ago. The client has a history of hypertension, a fractured humerus 15 months ago, and had chickenpox at 6 years of age. She is gravida 2, para 2. She exercises regularly by walking the family dog for 30 minutes daily. Her family history includes her father who had colon cancer and pulmonary tuberculosis, and her mother who has chronic renal failure and has had several transient ischemic attacks. The client denies smoking and drinks one glass of wine each day. She is allergic to sulfonamides and pollen. Current medications include metoprolol, norethindrone/ethynyl estradiol, and aspirin for headaches and muscle pain.

What are the factors that place this client at risk for developing a stroke?

Click to highlight the factors that place this client at risk for developing a stroke. Highlight only the risk factors for developing a stroke. To deselect a highlighted factor, click the factor again.

Read the case study below, then refer to the case study to answer the question.

The nurse is assessing a male client who has chronic renal failure and was admitted one day ago with bacterial pneumonia. The client's findings are listed below.

	Current	8 hours ago	24 hours ago
Blood pressure	136/84	138/86	134/82
Pulse	72	58	68
Respirations	16	14	12
Oral temperature	102.6° F (39.2° C)	100.3° F (37.9° C)	101.1° F (38.4° C)
Hemoglobin	11.5 g/dL (115 mmol/L)	12.8 g/dL (128 mmol/L)	13.5 g/dL (135 mmol/L)
Hematocrit	32 (0.32)	36 (0.36)	42 (0.42)
Platelet count	221,000/mm ³ (221 x 10 ⁹ /L)	223,400/mm ³ (223.4 x 10 ⁹ /L)	220,800/mm ³ (220.8 x 10 ⁹ /L)
White blood cell count	15,200/mm ³ (15.2 x 10 ⁹ /L)	15,300/mm ³ (15.3 x 10 ⁹ /L)	15,300/mm ³ (15.3 x 10 ⁹ /L)
Prothrombin time	12.1 seconds	12.2 seconds	12.3 seconds
Partial thromboplastin time	28 seconds	27 seconds	25 seconds
Serum potassium	5.3 mEq/L (5.3 mmol/L)	4.8 mEq/L (4.8 mmol/L)	4.5 mEq/L (4.5 mmol/L)
Serum sodium	142 mEq/L (142 mmol/L)	140 mEq/L (140 mmol/L)	143 mEq/L (143 mmol/L)
Blood urea nitrogen	52 mg/dL (18.6 mmol/L)	55 mg/dL (19.6 mmol/L)	51 mg/dL (18.2 mmol/L)
Serum creatinine	8.0 mg/dL (707.2 μmol/L)	8.2 mg/dL (724.9 μmol/L)	8.1 mg/dL (716.0 μmol/L)
Weight	210 lb (95.5 kg)	209 lb (95 kg)	206 lb (93.6 kg)
Edema	1+ pitting pedal	2+ pitting pedal	2+ pitting pedal
Urine output	23 mL/h	21 mL/h	24 mL/h

Which of the findings would be essential to follow up?

Click row(s) to highlight the finding(s) that would be essential to follow-up. Highlight only row(s) that require follow-up. To deselect a row, click the row again.

Read the following case study, then refer to the case study to answer the questions.

The nurse is caring for an 8-year-old client who experienced a cervical spinal cord injury four days ago and is receiving mechanical ventilation. The Progress Note is listed below.

Progress Notes

1410 The client received a nebulized bronchodilator treatment followed by chest physiotherapy and suctioning 15 minutes ago.

Which of the following findings should the nurse use to evaluate the effectiveness of the bronchodilator, suctioning and chest physiotherapy? Drag the four most important findings to the box on the right.

Findings

oxygen saturation level

arterial blood gas results

respiratory rate

presence of abdominal distention

chest x-ray results

respiratory effort

breath sounds

Four most important findings

Research Motivation

- Identify if additional information can be obtained from MR items
- Use of scoring methods beyond all correct/incorrect
 - Signal-detection theory (DeCarlo, 1998, 2011; Rouder & Lu, 2005)
 - Subsets of the correct answer set, e.g. normal partial credit models
 - True/False testlet model (Muntean & Betts, 2015)
- Evaluate methods for providing useful feedback to SME/CD
 - Traditional classical statistics might not be helpful

Signal-Detection Model

- Theoretical framework evaluate choice/decision making (Green & Swet, 1966; Luce, 1959)
- Recognize relevant from irrelevant cues
 - Keyed answers are relevant (+) and non-keyed are irrelevant (-), allows for detection of FP and FN responding
- Separate two important aspects of psychological process
 - Sensitivity: how accurately one can make correct judgments & avoid incorrect ones
 - Similar to item difficulty
 - Bias: extent of over/under endorsement related to optimal responding

Recognition Accuracy

- Discrimination (d'): measure of the distance between correct and incorrect response distributions
- Bias (c): distance from optimal responding

Recognition Accuracy

- Signal-detection theory (DeCarlo, 1998; 2010; 2011; 2012)

$$P(y = 1|S) = \Phi((\Psi_S - c)/\tau)$$

$$P(y = 1|N) = \Phi((\Psi_N - c)/\tau)$$

$$P(y = 1|X) = \Phi\left(\frac{\Psi_N - c}{\tau} + \frac{\Psi_S - \Psi_N}{\tau}X\right)$$

$$P(y = 1|X) = \Phi(c + dX)$$

$$P(y_{ij} = 1|c_i, d_i, \alpha_j, \delta_j, \mathbf{X}) = \Phi\left(c_i + d_i\mathbf{X} - (\alpha_j + \delta_j\mathbf{X})\right)$$

Subset Model

- Scoring rule:
 - Only subsets of the correct answer key set are considered partially correct
 - Any endorsement of incorrect option results in Score = 0
- Potentially useful when partial knowledge/skill should be rewarded
- Allows for assigning multiple score categories to an item

- Some important considerations:
 - What scoring rubric is best & is category collapsing necessary?
 - Are all subsets of the correct answer set relevant/scorable?
 - Do all subsets of the same cardinality represent the same level of ability?

True/False Testlet Model

	Endorse	Ignore
Valid	1	0
Invalid	0	1

- Potentially flexible model
 - Combines testlet model (Wainer & Kelly, 1987) with SDT concept
- Scoring rule:
 - All response options are nested in a common stimulus
 - Each response option is treated as a unique 'cue'
 - Scored as T/F (+/-) or Relevant/Irrelevant
- Potentially useful when non-endorsement is as important as endorsement
 - Ex. cue recognition, evaluating outcomes, taking action, etc.
- Some important considerations:
 - Same as subset model
 - What constraints to put on responding behavior, e.g. someone that just endorses all options?

Methods

- Participants (N = 9, 132) answered from 4 to 8 items
 - Randomly seeded into exam
- MR Items = 139
 - Between 400 and 600 responses per item
 - Stems: “Choose ALL that apply ...”
- Evaluate items with a number of scoring approaches
 - Rasch model (base)
 - Partial Credit Model (PCM; Masters, 1982) for (1) T/F ; (2) Subset models
 - SDT
- Evaluate the utility of parameters for providing useful feedback to SME/CDs

Correlations

	Item_Dif_TrueFalse	Item_Dif_SubSet	Item_Dif_SDT	Item_Bias_SDT
Item_Dif_Rasch	.852	.893	-.871	.265
Item_Dif_TrueFalse		.804	-.890	.289
Item_Dif_SubSet			-.808	.543
Item_Dif_SDT				-.162

True/False Partial Credit Model

Subset Partial Credit Model

Some Visualizations: Interesting Cases

- Normal Example
- NOTE: only response sets with > 20 responses are shown

- Low 'c' item: notice the under endorsement
- Normal looking item
 - {1, 3} common subset
 - {2, 5} little more difficult to endorse

- High 'c' item: notice the over endorsement
- 2 large, high-ability groups also endorsed '4'
- Are '3' and '4' potentially correct or even 'not incorrect'

- A large, high-ability group also endorsed '3'
- Also, all groups with higher average theta endorsed '3'
- Is '3' a potentially correct answer or just a very sweet distractor?

- Example where subsets of similar cardinality could have differences in ability
- {1, 3} NE {1,5} or {3,5}

Conclusions

- Different models can map to distinct cognitive processes
- All models appear to be very similar w.r.t. difficulty
 - IRT models provide a structure for category scaling
 - SDT provides information on responding bias – not highly correlated with difficulty
 - SDT can isolate recognition errors, sensitivity vs. bias
- Useful approaches to provide item level feedback to SME/CDs
- Possible future investigations:
 - Using the SDT model for individuals – profile of individual bias

Questions?

Thank You